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Nation-building in pre-federal and federal Ethiopia (1855-2019): Analysis of the language policy role, pattern, and consequence

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Abstract

This paper analyzes Ethiopia's nation-building processes and the language policy role, pattern, and consequence both in pre-federal (1855-1991) and federal (1991-2019) Ethiopia through a comparative lens. The study employed primary and secondary data sources, including official documents, books, and journal articles. The findings revealed that Ethiopia's nation-building processes and its language policy remain incompatible with a multiethnic polity-building model that promotes unity in diversity. While the pre-federal Ethiopia's nation-building model was based on a cultural assimilation policy, the federal Ethiopia under the EPRDF era (1991-2019), though it recognized ethno-cultural diversity, failed to adopt inclusive multicultural citizenship and nested identities. The state's failure to adopt an inclusive multicultural citizenship and nested identities induced the erosion of state legitimacy, hardened ethno-national mobilization, and deepened social divide expressed in the form of political polarization. Thus, this study suggests that Ethiopia needs to adopt a multiethnic polity-building model that horizontally grants adequate autonomy to assert diversity and promote nested identities and vertically promotes inclusive multicultural citizenship for the realization of an inclusive multiethnic polity that keeps unity in diversity in harmony.

Keywords: language policy, federalism, autonomy, nested identities, multiethnic polity-building.

1. Introduction

Multiethnic polity-building is defined as a nation-building model that aims to build a political community of sentiment within cultural diversity by choice and reflection of the diverse ethnic groups composing the polity adopting autonomy, multicultural policies, and promoting nested identities. A multiethnic polity-building model not only recognizes ethno-cultural diversity but also promotes nested identities and

inclusive citizenship at national level. Promoting inclusive civic values such as national flag, national anthem, and collective national narratives regarding ethnic, linguistic, cultural, historical values of the polity and focusing on a democratic constitutional system is an integral part of a multiethnic polity-building model (Assefa, 2023).

Language policy is part of public policies that plays crucial role in shaping the nation-building model. A monolingual language policy yields nation-state building model, multilingual policy yields a multiethnic polity-building model that promotes national unity in diversity (McGarry & O’Leary, 2003).

A nation-state building model uses a certain narrowly defined public values, which in reality is the values of a core ethnic group in the polity — which is simply a dominant majority group, or in its absence, a titular nation in control of political power of state (Assefa, 2023). By contrast, a multiethnic polity-building model promotes national unity within diversity by granting autonomy¹ to self-rule for asserting diversity and adopting multicultural citizenship and inclusive institutions at national or shared-rule level to promote inclusive multicultural citizenship (Kymlicka, 1995)

In a broader sense, language policy consists of four major policies within itself: (I), Official language policy that relates to the business of administration for public service delivery either at national level or sub-national level; (II) Educational language policy that relates to medium of instruction in schools and language subject(s) taught in a formal education; (III), Media language policy relating to medium of broadcasting, and finally, (VI), Language policy as an integral part of human rights (Cooper, 1989; Tollefson & Pérez-Milans, 2018).

¹Autonomy refers to the privileges of a given ethnic identity group to assert their self-identity. Autonomy includes political autonomy, administrative autonomy, fiscal autonomy, or cultural autonomy.

When it comes ethnic composition of Ethiopia, is just beyond a multiethnic country in the sense that its diversity transcends multiethnic identity due to the fact that these ethnic groups have become self-conscious and mobilized entities demanding autonomy to self-rule to assert their self-identity and vertically also demanding inclusive multicultural citizenship opposing to the “nation-state” building model that has been in place since the inception of modern state of Ethiopia during the imperial era in the second half of the 19th century, promoting only a certain ethnic group’s identities as the sole national identity of Ethiopia, including its official language, culture, and religion (Markakis, 1974).

The beginning of Ethiopia’s nation-building model roughly traces back to the rise of Emperor Tewodros II in 1855 by subduing powerful regional lords of the time, including *Ras Ali II of Yejju* (1853) and *Dejazmach Wube of Semien and Tigray* (1855) that weakened central authority during the Era of Princes (*Zemana Masafinit*) (c. 1769- 1855) (Bahru, 2002).

Ethiopia’s nation-building processes for most part of its history is defined by power centralization and cultural assimilation policy and, which in turn caused ethno-national mobilization demanding autonomy to self-rule for asserting diversity and inclusive national equality since the mid-1960s. The state’s effort to build a nation-state model out of diversity prompted ethno-national mobilization signaling the political path of the state toward inclusive federalism (Merera, 2003).

In the mid-1960s onwards, numerous ethnic groups came to demand autonomy to self-rule to assert diversity along with fair representation at national level. Thus, a nation-state model that might have worked in those states with a core nation has failed in Ethiopia for the fact that Ethiopia lacks any core ethnic group that absorbs ethno-cultural groups. A core ethnic group which represents at least 60% of the total population is needed for successful realization of the nation-state building project in any country by effectively absorbing the existing ethnic minorities (McGarry & O'Leary, 2003). Ethiopia however remains *a land of ethnic minorities* lacking any particular ethnic group that forms at least 60% of the total population of the country.

Even though Ethiopia owns relative majority ethnic groups such as Oromo 34.5% (25.4 million) and Amhara 26.9% (19.8 million), neither of them is a core ethnic group that unilaterally constitutes at least 60% of the total population. As a result, the imperial rule of assimilation and power centralization policy, including the *Derg* regime failed to succeed. The coalition of ethno-nationalist forces — the Ethiopian Peoples' Revolutionary Democratic Front (EPRDF) took power removing the *Derg* regime in May 1991. EPRDF regime also failed to realize the strong claims of ethno-national groups for asserting cultural diversity and promoting inclusive multicultural citizenship.

The Prosperity Party (PP) then substituted the EPRDF regime in Dec 2019 following the protracted public protest beginning from 2018 in Oromia and Amhara regions. EPRDF, which was a political coalition of multiethnic political parties in Ethiopia (r. 1991-2019), was now replaced by the incumbent ruling party known as the Prosperity Party in Dec. 2019 as a unified version of EPRDF excluding the Tigray People's Liberation Front (TPLF).

2. Materials and Methods

It employed a comparative analytical approach with a qualitative method of data collection and analysis using official documents, books, and journal articles in analyzing the language policy role, pattern, and consequence in nation-building process in the pre-federal and federal Ethiopia which covered Imperial era (1855-1974), *Derg* era (1974-1991), and EPRDF era (1991-2019). It addressed the following basic research questions: What were the role, pattern, and consequence of the language policy in Ethiopia's nation-building processes in three successive eras? How significantly different was one era from the next in terms of nation-building model and language policy? What type of language policy and nation-building model suites for Ethiopia which owns numerous ethno-national groups with demands of autonomy to self-rule to assert diversity and fair representation at national level to promote and ensure inclusive multicultural citizenship?

3. Nation-building and State-building

Nation-building models are broadly classified into four categories:

(I). Nation-state building model (bəḥērā-mānəgəsət gənəbata): it is essentially defined by promoting national unity through cultural assimilation by adopting cultural assimilation policies and centralized institutions without any official recognition of the existing ethno-cultural diversity.

(II). Civic nation-building and/or state-nation building model (mānəgəsətā-bəḥēr gənəbata): it is defined by promoting national unity through liberal integration approach with recognition of cultural minorities but without giving space for accommodating diversity with institutional mechanism or support.

(III). Multiethnic polity-building building and/ or nation-by-will model (ḥəbərābəḥērā-mānəgəsət gənəbata): it is defined by building national unity in diversity granting adequate autonomy to self-rule and ensuring devolved institutions and multicultural policies for achieving inclusive multicultural citizenship.

(IV). Multinational and/or Plurinational state-building model (bəzəhabəḥērā-mānəgəsət gənəbata) defined by promoting diversity with little regard for promoting shared national unity focusing on diversity and lacking nested identities and inclusive multiculturalism at national level. Unlike a multiethnic polity- building model which moderates between self-identity and shared-national identities, plurinational state model fails to balance the two equations of self and shared identities.

On the other hand, the concept of state-building (ḥägārā-mānəgəsət gənəbata) relates to promoting public institutions such as bureaucracy, healthcare, justice, security system, infrastructures like roads, electricity, water supply, housing, and so forth.

State-building focuses on consolidating political institutions and governance structures to create a stable, functional political system that provides security, enforces laws and policies, and delivers public services to its society (Assefa, 2023). Key elements of state-building include developing legal and political institutions; building a capacity on monopoly use of force such as police, military; administrative capacity for public services; and promoting rule of law and democratic governance; and infrastructure, including road and transportation facilities, communication, electricity, water supply, education, and healthcare (Assefa, 2023).

In fact, the relationship between nation-building and state-building often overlaps and influences each other, or even in some cases interchangeably used as they are inseparable components like a hardware (state-building) and software (nation- building) entities, in which state-building plays *foundational* role, nation-building plays a *catalyst* role (Assefa, 2023).

3.1. Multiethnic polity-building model and its core pillars

Multiethnic polity-building model (nation-by-will) model promotes unity in cultural diversity horizontally granting autonomy for self-rule to assert cultural diversity and vertically adopting multicultural policies to ensure inclusive multicultural citizenship. A multiethnic polity-building model holds five major pillars: a democratic regime; shared-rule; self-rule; Intergovernmental Relations IGR; building nested identities or blending self-identity with collective civic identities ensuring dual allegiance (Stepan, 1999). A constitutional democratic regime entails that shared-rule and self-rule units must be fundamentally guided by an established constitutional democracy.

Similarly, the shared rule unit has to adopt inclusive multicultural policies that promote cohesive multicultural citizenship addressing the vertical quest for inclusive citizenship. Multicultural policies play crucial role for building nested identities. On the other hand, self-rule units while asserting diversity need to promote nested identities by encouraging their ethnic groups of people to show dual loyalties blending local self-identity and collective civic values.

Autonomy to self-rule that addresses the quest for asserting/promoting diversity should not undermine the loyalty to the overarching national identity. And, there must be intergovernmental relations (IGR) facilitating smooth institutional relations vertically between the union government and self-rule regional unit and horizontally between member states of the federation. Finally, promoting nested identities by blending the local and national sets of identities is required in a way that one set of identity do not undermine the other one to uphold an inclusive multicultural citizenship within ethno-cultural diversity.

In other words, individuals and groups in a multiethnic polity should be able to identify themselves with their own local identity and equally with their own larger political unit. For instance, in some cases, in Ethiopia, some people may tend to identify themselves with more of their ethnic nationalities prioritizing over their civic national identity and this is what is referred to as a lack of building nested identities (Assefa, 2023; Stepan, 1999).

Fostering nested identities helps citizens to identify themselves simultaneously with their local identity and the broader union or national identity. Such policies need to be promoted at shared rule as well as self-rule units. Collective/shared civic identity includes symbols as constitution, national anthem, national flag, national narratives that incorporate diverse identities as the integral part of the multicultural nation. By the same token, at the self-rule level, there should be policies of fostering nested identities that not only assert diversity but also encourage blending self-identity with the larger national union identities to keep unity and diversity in harmony. However, if the union (shared-rule) government is undemocratic and oppressive regime that fails to adopt multicultural policies and devolved institutions for asserting and promoting multiethnic and multicultural cohesion, promoting unity in diversity fails.

Source: adapted based on theoretical framework, 2024

Figure 1: Multiethnic polity-building model.

3.2. Distinction between nation-state and multinational state/nation of nations

The origin of modern state in Europe traces back to the 17th century with the Treaty of Westphalia (1648) recognizing the state sovereignty within its own jurisdiction, or otherwise prohibiting a state interference from the internal matters of another states. From the time of the Westphalia Treaty to the mid-20th century, the term modern state was equated with a nation-state regardless of cultural diversity within. Sovereign states are named as nation-states regardless of cultural diversity within the state. On the other hand, since the aftermath of WWI (1914-18) mobilized ethno-national groups emerged as the integral part of human rights revolution within the state demanding autonomy to self-determination and including secession (Moore, 1998).

The right to self-determination of people was also encouraged by the superpowers of the United States and Soviet Union, which gave rise to the proliferation of ethno-national mobilization in a given sovereign state causing the advent of multinational states or nations of nations as such recognition to self-determination of people generated several nations within the state. Therefore, nowadays, the term — nation could mean not only a sovereign state as before but also any politically mobilized ethno-national group demanding autonomy to self-rule or otherwise complete political independence from the broader political union. The conventional description of all sovereign states as nations is reflected in the “United Nations” regardless of the country’s ethno-cultural composition. Any state is commonly named as a “nation” in a polity sense irrespective of its diversity

Nationalism or the doctrine of nation-building ideology traces back to the late 18th century with the American Revolution or Declaration of Independence (1776) against British Imperialism and French Revolution (1789) against its own absolute Monarchy, which shed light on evolution of popular sovereignty serving as center of democratic rule. Nationalism began to serve as means of nation-state building in the mid-19th c. with Italian and German unification in 1871 (Hyslop, 1960). After the defeat of socialism and the subsequent ruin of the Soviet Union and the break of the Berlin Wall in 1989, nationalism has gained momentum and which caused east and west Germans to be (re)united in 1990 as they believed to belong to the same nation (Moore, 1998).

⁵Although the UK is commonly regarded as a unitary system, however, practically it remains a *de facto* federal system by all metrics of power devolution among its constituent units.

⁶The term national language and official language have distinct meanings. While

within based on the assumption that it is formed by free popular will as a political unit.

Multinational states differ from nation-states in terms of needs of asserting cultural diversity and promoting inclusive multicultural citizenship (Buchanan, 1991; Tierney, 2005). While promoting singular citizenship may suffice for nation-states, it requires granting autonomy and promoting multicultural citizenship for a nation of nations. For example, Quebec of Canada, Catalonia and Basque of Spain, Northern Ireland and Scotland of the UK⁵, Flemish of Belgium, and Kurds in the Middle East, including Turkey, Iraq, Iran, and Syria, and dozens of ethno-national groups in Ethiopia have needs of autonomy to self-rule for asserting diversity and promoting inclusive multicultural citizenship (Assefa, 2023; Bengio, 2007; Brubaker, 1996). Switzerland is, for instance, multicultural state with four national languages⁶, including German, French, Italian, and Romansh (Berthele, 2021).

national language is associated with languages playing vital role in cultural and social identity formation of a nation representing larger ethno-linguistic heritage, official language relates to languages providing formal official service for governance and official communication. In many cases, official languages may not be endorsed as national language, particularly in a context of linguistically plural polities since it is a delicate issue raising issues of inclusion or exclusion. As a result, it is tacitly understood that official language is a default national language in such cases. For instance, South Africa has 11 official languages, including English yet none of them is explicitly endorsed as a national language.

However, it doesn’t mean that South Africa has no any national language. In fact, isiZulu, isiXhosa, and Afrikaans are *understandably* South Africa’s national languages for their socio-cultural role. Similarly, Amharic was/is Ethiopia’s official and national language explicitly or implicitly.

Multinational states such as Ethiopia, Belgium, Canada, etc., possess multiple ethnic-nations within themselves and such groups evolve as a result of a nation-state building model (in most cases) that represses cultural diversity. For example, Quebec of Canada, Catalonia and Basque of Spain, Flemish of Belgium, and Kurds in the Middle East and ethno-national groups in Ethiopia are the product of the nation-state building model carried out by the ethno-respective regimes (See Assefa, 2023; Bengio, 2007; Brubaker, 1996).

As earlier implied, nation-state building model pursue assimilation promoting unity in cultural uniformity based on state-favored —civic identity without liberal multicultural policies that recognizes and tolerates diversity and without institutional support for promoting group-differentiated rights. A liberal integration variant of civic-nation or state-nation model tolerates diversity but without institutional support for promoting diversity. This model has always been promoted by the International Organizations such as the United Nations, International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank. Western states with core nations, including United States, Germany, France, the Netherlands, and Austria have actually succeeded with liberal integration model (Kymlicka, 1995; Stepan, 1999; McGarry & O’leary, 2003). However, several studies assert liberal integration model doesn’t succeed in multicultural states devoid of a core nation since simple liberal answers such as non-discrimination, and undifferentiated citizenship, civic national equality without institutional support for promoting diversity don’t suffice to address the question of ethno-national groups demanding for asserting

cultural diversity and ensuring inclusive multicultural citizenship (Kymlicka, 1995; Stepan, 1999; McGarry & O’leary, 2003).

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Imperial era’s language policy and nation-building model (1855-1974)

Although the reign of Emperor Tewodros II signified the beginning of modern state-building process in Ethiopia, the origin of the historic Ethiopian polity traces back to the Aksumite Kingdom in the 1st century AD, which was framed and shaped based on the mores of the Northern highland plateau commonly known as Abyssinian and the values of Orthodox Christianity following King Ezana’s conversion to Christianity in the early 4th century (in 330 AD) (Sergew, 1972). The reign of Emperor Tewodros II (r. 1855-1868) was a turning point in the process of Ethiopia’s modern state system realizing centralization and state sovereignty, subduing strong regional lords that undermined central authority, including *Ras Ali II* in 1853, *Dejazmach Wube* in 1855, and King *Haile Meleket* in 1855. In doing so, Emperor Tewodros II was able to abolish fragmented regional rules in Ethiopia and paved the way for modern nation-state building overcoming the Era of Princes also known as *Zemana Mesafint* which lasted for nearly a century (c. 1769-1855).

Regarding the language policy, Emperor Tewodros II declared Amharic as literary language of the royal court replacing the previously literary language known as Geéz.⁷ Amharic then gained the status

⁷ Ge’ez, which is now confined to liturgical service in the Ethiopian Orthodox Church, was once the literary (written) and spoken language of the royal Court (the Palace) notably during the Aksumite Kingdom (c. 1st century AD-10th century AD). Amharic replaced Ge’ez as spoken language

being literary/written language of the court (Bender, 1983). The monolingual language policy started with Tewodros II continued to shape Ethiopia's nation-state building model based on a certain narrowly defined public identity. The nation-state building model in Ethiopia also involved the mores of the Northern Plateau (aka Abyssinian custom) with a hierarchical political norm and Orthodox Christianity (Merera, 2003).

On the other hand, Emperor Yohannes IV (r.1872-1889) the late successor of Tewodros II, although ideally remained absolute Monarch, unlike his predecessor began to devolve autonomy to the various regional rulers. For instance, the *Litché* Agreement (1878) was concluded between Emperor Yohannes IV and King Menelik of Shoa. In this agreement while Menelik recognized the suzerainty of Emperor Yohannes, the latter was also reciprocated with formal recognition as provincial king of Shoa. Similarly, *Ras* Adal of Gojjam was elevated to King Tekle Haymanot in 1881 for his submission to the Emperor; *Ras* Michael (formerly Mohamed Ali) was granted administrative autonomy to rule over the province Wollo for his conversion to Orthodox Christianity (Crummey, 2000; Marcus, 1994).

The reign of Emperor Yohannes IV was therefore characterized by a *quasi-federal system* in the sense that regional autonomy

of the Court following the decline of the Aksumite kingdom and the rise of the Zagwe Dynasty (c. 10th century AD-13th century AD). Gə'əz maintained its literary language status until the reign of Tewodros II (r.1855-1868). Emperor Tewodros II promoted Amharic as literary language overtaking the role of Gə'əz. Besides serving as the literary language of the Court in pre-federal and federal Ethiopia alike, Amharic continues to be the single most important language playing the role of lingua franca language ensuring a wider communication in diverse ethno-linguistic communities of Ethiopia.

was officially granted as long as the regional rules were willing to pay tributes to the Emperor. However, with regard to the pattern of the language policy under Emperor Yohannes IV, the mono-lingual language policy remained the same despite provision of administrative autonomy to the regional vassals. In fact, in terms religious tolerance, Emperor Yohannes IV was even more conservative than his predecessor as was crystal clear in the Council of Boru Media (1878), where Muslim aristocrats of the Wollo region were forced to follow Christianity, or leave their position in government (Rubenson, 1987). The reign of Emperor Yohannes IV was a proof that granting autonomy alone without adopting multicultural policies remains inadequate to promote inclusive-polity building as polity-building requires autonomy and multicultural policies for promoting inclusive citizenship. In this case, devolution of power, including federalism doesn't make any difference in nation-building process unless autonomy is accompanied by multicultural policies.

Emperor Menelik II (r. 1889-1913) was another key political figure in modern state formation of Ethiopia.⁸ The victory of Adwa (in 1896) against the colonial power of Italy was remarkable achievement under his reign, which played decisive role in securing international recognition by super powers, including Great Britain, France, Russia, and Italy itself, which also enabled to him expand the state territory, and open

⁸Emperor Menelik II was King of Shoa (r.1866-1889) and Emperor of Ethiopia (r.1889-1913) started unifying the land and people of the South, Southwest and East into Ethiopia's empire, which took two decades (1878-1898) to complete the empire-state building project. This period of incorporation is referred to (by some) as *hägär maqənat* roughly translated as — cultivation/ Christianization/ civilization of the people (Bahru, 2002).

up a formal diplomatic relations with the aforementioned Europeans powers (Bahru, 2002). Unlike his predecessor, Emperor Menelik II reinforced power centralization by centrally appointing regional rulers, particularly in those newly incorporated territories with resistance (Marcus, 1994).

With regard to the language policy during this time, Amharic continued as a symbol of unity despite incorporation of huge ethno-linguistic diversity after the robust territorial expansion project, which raised the demographic and territorial size of the empire by three-fold (Markakis, 1974). Irrespective of ethno-linguistic diversity, The implicit monolingual language policy continued to dictate Ethiopia's nation-state building process based on the already established nation-state building model, including language, culture, and religion. This time around, the local elites continued to adopt the values of the *ruling class*, including language, culture, and religion; and were reciprocated with recognition, local authority, and even were able to establish intermarriages with the royal families (Cohen, 2000).

It was also during the reign of Emperor Menelik II that modern education system started. The first modern school, Menelik II School, was opened up in 1908, and French was compulsory language used as medium of instruction and taught as a subject until it was replaced by English in 1947 after nearly four decades of use (Bloor & Tamrat, 1996). The curriculum during this time also included other languages, including English, Italian, and Arabic on selective basis (Bloor & Tamrat, 1996). The modern education system during this time focused on producing skilled officials who would play roles in diplomatic functions acquiring

international languages, including French, Italian, Arabic, and English (Seyoum, 1996).

Emperor Haile Selassie I (r. 1930-1974) was another crucial political figure in attaining the peak of power centralization and cultural assimilation policy in his effort to realize a nation-state building project, particularly after his return home from exile (as Ethiopia was occupied by Italy for a brief period from 1936-1941). The revised imperial constitution known as the 1955 constitution in article 125 stated that, —Amharic is the official language of the Ethiopian Empire, which highlighted the continuance of the monolingual policy. The monolingual policy during this time was even more reinforced by the education policy. Amharic was promoted as a sole local language serving as a medium of instruction in primary schools (from grade 1-6) and taught as a subject both in primary and secondary schools across the country without any space for other local languages (Bloor & Tamrat, 1996). However, it must not be forgotten that a *foreign language* (English) has always been a *de facto* co-official language in Ethiopia appearing side by side with Amharic, including in currency and other national symbols since 1947 as the country switched from Francophone orientation to Anglophone (Teshome, 1997).

Unfortunately, all attempts of nation-state building ended with tragic consequences inducing mobilized ethno-national groups, demanding autonomy to self-rule for asserting diversity as well as inclusive multicultural policies for prompting and ensuring multicultural citizenship. The dire consequence of the monolithic nation-state building in the Imperial Ethiopia include the rise of competing nationalism, eroded state legitimacy, political polarization

along ethno-linguistic markers, social divide, mistrust, and hostility, and regime instability (Assefa 2010; Merera 2003).

Although crafting shared *lingua franca* language for diverse countries such as Ethiopia is crucial so as to ensure a wider communication, other local languages also should have been given opportunity as means of accommodating diversity. As a result of the state failure to accommodate diversity, the state faced dire consequence incubating mobilized groups in the late 1960s. For instance, in the 1970s various liberation forces were formed like Eritrean People Liberation Front (EPLF) (1972), Oromo Liberation Front (OLF) (1973), Tigray People Liberation Front (TPLF) (1975), Western Somalia Liberation Front (WSLF) (1975), and Sidama Liberation Movement (SLM) (1978), and later the Ogaden National Liberation Front (ONLF) (1984) (Bahru 2002; Henze, 2000).

4.2. Derg's language policy and nation-building model (1974-1991)

Following Ethiopia's Social Revolution (1974), Military Junta otherwise known as *Derg* took power on 2 September 1974. *Derg* switched the state ideology from feudal theocracy to garrison socialism. As compared to Imperial era, *Derg* showed a positive gesture towards multiculturalism recognizing diverse ethno-national groups with constitutional affirmation, which somehow switched the country's nation-building model from *assimilation* variant to *liberal integration* variant of nation-building as the state began to recognize the presence of diverse ethno-national groups. Unlike Imperial era, *Derg* launched what was known as the —National Democratic Revolution Program of the Socialist Ethiopial in 1976 in the effort to promote

the history, culture, and language of the NNPs (Bender, 1985). Regarding this, Lionel Bender made the following remark:

The military government which replaced the Haile Silassie's regime in Ethiopia in 1974 has followed much the same language policy as its predecessor: promoting Amharic as national language. However, it is moderated by a self-conscious attitude of attention to national minorities and is (masked) in so-called Marxist-Leninist propaganda. Progress is slow because of the continued state of civil war in Ethiopia (itself a sign of centrifugal forces at work) and the lack of skilled planners and technicians (Bender, 1985: 173).

In comparison to the imperial era, nation-building process during *Derg* switched from assimilation to a sort of liberal integration. The (re)opening of —Ethiopian Languages and Cultures Academy in 1976 was also another step that indicated *Derg* had a tendency towards multilingual language policy and planning.⁹ The Academy was assigned to create alphabets for those nationalities' languages without writing systems, and prepare dictionaries and grammar books. Its implementation was however undermined by socialism which regards nationalism as mere false consciousness that would fade away as class distinction is abolished. Socialism envisioned that post-national cosmopolitan world order would be restored (Nodia,

⁹ Language planning constitutes corpus planning, status planning, or acquisition planning. Corpus planning relates to standardizing and/or advancing the linguistic structure of a language, including the creation of dictionaries, grammar books, forming new writing system, and initiating reform. Status planning relates to the allocation of new function to a language such as using the language as medium of instruction or an official language. Acquisition planning relates to efforts to spread a language providing access to learn the language (Cooper, 1989).

2017). During this time even federalism was used as a means to soften nationalism in efforts to create a cosmopolitan post-national order as in the case of the failed federations of Eastern Europe, including Yugoslavia in 1992, Soviet Union in 1989, and Czechoslovakia in 1993, and which were sham federations with ethnic form but socialist in content, which were not meant to fulfill demands of ethnic groups but rather for to attain the vision of socialism as a political order (McGarry & O'leary, 2003).

Moreover, *Derg* established the —Institute for the Study of Ethiopian Nationalities with the 1983 legislation. This Institute was assigned various tasks, including conducting research on the nationalities (referring to the various mobilized ethno-national groups and other ethno-cultural groups), identifying their geographical locations, and documenting their cultures and languages.¹⁰ The 1987 Constitution (which is notionally the first Ethiopian Republic) stressing its commitment to ensure equality, development, and respect for the languages of the nationalities, however, paradoxically article 116 of the same constitution declared that, —Amharic is the working language of the state without leaving space for other languages in the country as co-official language. As the state remained heavily centralized, it was incapable of devolving autonomy to the various ethno-national groups. Thus, the constitutional promise to promote diversity, including language remained a symbolic gesture without translating into actual practice (Bender, 1985: 274).

¹⁰A proclamation set to provide for the establishment of the institute for the study of Ethiopian nationalities, Proclamation No.236 of 1983.

Additional *Derg* effort which is worth of mentioning here is the —National Literacy Campaign started in 1975 and continued throughout 1980s, intending to raise the literacy rate of its people with an informal education using multiple local languages as medium of instruction, including Amharic, Afaan Oromo, Somali, Tigire, Tigrinya, Wolaita, Sidama, Haddiya, Kambata, Afar, Saho, Gedeo, Kafinono, Silti, and Kunama (Hailu 1993, as quoted in Zelealem, 2012: 24).

Unfortunately, *Derg's* language policy in an informal education system failed to translate into a formal education system. Amharic remained the sole local language as medium of instruction and language subject to be taught at a formal education (Bloor & Tamrat, 1996). Competing nationalism (i.e., state nationalism and its opposing ethno-nationalism continued to undermine unity and territorial integrity of the state, however (Bender, 1985). The nation-building process that shifted from the hitherto assimilation policy to liberal integration variant failed to stop the mobilized ethno-nationalist forces from demanding autonomy to self-rule for asserting/promoting diversity and inclusive multicultural policies. After the protracted *civil war* between the centrist-state and the insurgent ethno-national forces, *Derg* was eventually defeated and the state power was controlled by the ethno-nationalist forces in May 1991.

4.3. EPRDF's language policy and nation-building model (1991-2019)

EPRDF, which came to power ousting *Derg*, restructured Ethiopia into (mainly) ethnic-based federation with the intent to address the long-standing question of self-determination rights and ensuring national equality horizontally granting autonomy

for asserting self-identity and vertically promoting inclusive citizenship. EPRDF installed a federal system based on ethno-territoriality principle in way to address the aforementioned quests coupled with popular consent which was a major tool used in federalization process of Ethiopia (Assefa, 2010).

In other words, non-territorial minorities have been out of sight of the constitutional framers, and which has undoubtedly significantly jeopardized the civil and political rights of the non-titular minorities inhabiting out of their own predefined homeland territories (Assefa, 2016). As stated in the preamble of the 1995 FDRE constitution, Ethiopia's federation is supposed to be a federation of ethno-national groups or in the vernacular of the 1995 Constitution — Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples (NNPs) having unconditional right to self-determination (See article 39 (1)). There are 76 recognized NNPs with seats in the House of Federation (HoF), which should not be confused with ethno-linguistic groups however in which case there are over 85 ethno-linguistic groups (See the 2007 census). As per the 1995 Constitution, the NNPs have proportionate seat in the HoF (see Art. 61(2)). Ethiopia's federalism is an *asymmetric* in the sense that there is disparity in autonomy among the NNPs. While some NNPs are endowed with regional autonomy; most of them are endowed with local autonomy. However, in light of institutional setting, Ethiopian federation is a *symmetric* as all regional units are endowed with equal rights and power (See 47/4).

Ethiopia now has twelve constituent units and/or regional states, including Tigray, Afar, Amhara, Oromia, Somali, Sidama, Beni/Gumuz, Gambella, Harari, Central Ethiopia, South west, and South Ethiopia.

In terms of addressing issues of the horizontal autonomy and the vertical inclusion, EPRDF era was better off as compared to the previous eras, particularly in addressing the horizontal questions — the quest for autonomy to assert diversity though there are disparities in autonomy among NNPs. For instance, pertaining to issues of granting autonomy to assert diversity, EPRDF was able to provide NNPs autonomy to self-rule at sub-national level. In doing so, some NNPs, including Oromia, Somali, Afar, Tigray, and Harari¹¹ that have been named after the respective titular NNPs managed to use their language as official language of the respective regional states. However, national minorities within the aforesaid regional states as well as vast majority of NNPs under multiethnic regional states such as Benishagul-Gumuz, and Gambella were not able to use their language as official language at self-rule level for such multiethnic arrangement poses challenges to adopt a particular language as official language of the respective regional states since such arrangement compels to adopt a *lingua franca language* to ensure a wider communication. In this case EPRDF was not able to satisfy all NNPs to use their language as official language at self-rule.

¹¹ Harari State is unique in its language policy adopting bi-official language policy. Harari is the smallest regional state of Ethiopian federation, which resembles a city-state encircled by the Oromia Regional State. Its capital Harar City is shared between Eastern Hararge Zone of Oromia Region and Harari State. Demographically, it is outnumbered by other inhabitants such as Oromo. Geographic and demographic factors appear to have compelled it to adopt co-official language policy of Afaan Oromo and Harari languages.

This is in fact one of the major challenges of Ethiopian federal system, which pushes NNPs to demand for further and exclusive regional autonomy and self-rule rather than cluster-based multiethnic regional autonomy and local self-rule. In other words, EPRDF was not able to deliver regional autonomy and regional self-rule to every NNP as promised by the 1995 constitution (See article 39 & 47). To this end, the post-EPRDF era, or otherwise the incumbent ruling Prosperity Party (PP) has been able to split the previously SNNPR, which constituted over 75% of the NNPs, into four regional states, including Central Ethiopia, Sidama, Southwest Ethiopia, and South Ethiopia regional states.

Moreover, regarding issues of promoting inclusive multicultural citizenship, EPRDF failed. The need for political reform was caused by public protest in different parts of the state notably Oromia and Amhara in quest for fair representation and inclusion and opposing maladministration and gross human rights violation by the regime and the state's failure to address such demands in different parts of the country. Regarding language policy as part of inclusive multicultural policies, EPRDF was not able to adopt multilingual policies at the national level despite adopting federal political system and multilingual policies at regional level.

NNPs under the EPRDF era continued to demand adequate autonomy to self-rule notably exclusive regional autonomy as in the case of Sidama, Gurage, Wolayita, Haddya, Kaffa, and inclusive multicultural policies for multicultural citizenship, and which continued to undermine political stability and social cohesion. EPRDF was not able to promote nested identities encouraging people to blend unity and

diversity equations in balance as it was mostly emphasizing on otherness.

The 1995 Constitution also declares that —Amharic is working language of the federal government¹², while the constituent units may adopt their own languages (see article 5(2-3)). As succinctly put, the language policy of Ethiopia is guided by *one lingua franca language thesis* rather than multiple *lingua franca languages* that advocate promoting one shared language to ensure a wider communication among diverse ethno-linguistic groups to bring about national unity, which is however against the gist of inclusive polity-building model that advocates multilingualism at the union/national level as the case of Switzerland, Canada, South Africa, India, and Belgium illustrates. These countries are all multicultural federations adopting multiple lingua franca language policies. As opposed to *one lingua franca thesis*, *multiple lingua franca language thesis* promotes multinational cohesion as in the case of Switzerland¹² that has four national languages, South Africa¹³ eleven official languages, India¹⁴ twenty-three official languages under the eighth schedule of the Indian constitution including English, Belgium¹⁵ has two (French and Dutch) federal official languages, and Canada¹⁶

¹²

<https://www.eda.admin.ch/aboutswitzerland/en/home/gesellschaft/sprachen.html>

¹³ https://www.statssa.gov.za/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Approved_Language_Policy_2018.pdf

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eighth_Schedule_to_the_Constitution_of_India

¹⁵ Van der Jeught, S. (2017). Territoriality and freedom of language: the case of Belgium. *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 18(2), 181-198.

¹⁶

<https://www.thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/language-policy>

two (English and French) federal official languages.

Last but not least, EPRDF also applied monolingual language policy in education teaching one local language, Amharic, as a subject across the country in primary and secondary schools to promote based on the thesis of *one lingua franca language* without offering space for more *lingua franca languages*. In other words, during EPRDF era, in addition to the monolingual official language policy, language policy in education followed suit promoting one *lingua franca language*, teaching one local language, Amharic, as a subject across the country without consideration for *multiple lingua franca languages* which has been therefore against the gist of an inclusive polity-building model. Therefore, it raises a question that how significantly did EPRDF's language policy and nation-building model differ from the pre-federal era? This question would be answered by looking into the self-rule autonomy that allowed most of the NNPs to use their own language as medium of instruction (for mother tongue education), or even in some cases, for enabling official language use at regional self-rule level such as Oromia, Tigray, Afar, Somali, and Harari though it remained monolingual at national level.

In a nutshell, when we closely look into the language policy in education during EPRDF era (r. 1991-2019) in terms of polity-building granting autonomy to self-rule and multicultural policies to promote inclusive citizenship, it has had significant limitations. The nation-building model was rather multinational-state model focusing on otherness/ diversity as it missed nested identities. Moreover, despite the presence of the multilingual language policy at self-rule level, only those NNPs with regional

autonomy have managed to use their own working languages in practice while the vast majority of NNPs have not been able to use their vernacular as official or even as co-official language at self-rule level despite constitutional promise to promote one's own language (see article 39/2). This has made the various groups in the country to push for autonomy and inclusive multicultural policy for asserting diversity and inclusive citizenship at national level.

As a result, following a formal substitution of EPRDF by PP in 2019, a new language policy evolved in February 2020, which has raised the federal working languages from the previous one language to five languages namely Amharic, Afaan Oromo, Tigrinya, Somali, and Afar selecting based on the criteria of a language of wider communication, a language with wider mother tongue speaker, and a language with trans-boundary nature shared by millions in the neighboring countries with a potential role for fostering economic, cultural, and diplomatic integration¹⁷ which would play significant role in terms of symbolic relevance though which is still contested that whether this language policy reform is adequate in a country where more than 80 languages are spoken. Moreover, in terms of language policy in education, the 2020 language policy has come up with a tri-lingual language policy urging students to learn at least three languages, including one's own mother tongue, a foreign language (English), and one local language from among the federal working language on selective basis. This will have also a positive role in terms of building inclusive polity-building process

¹⁷ LPFDRE (Language Policy of Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia), Ministry of Culture and Tourism, February 2020/Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

as it raises chances for learning multiple languages and thereby increasing chances for multiple lingua franca languages given the growing number of federal working languages. In fact, that is how inclusive polity-building model is realized.

5. Conclusion

Ethiopia's monolithic nation-state building model proved its unsuitability for one single most reason: a lack of core nation that effectively absorbs minorities and smoothly settles any resistance against the *status quo*. The consequence of this model has remained tragic resulting in competing nationalism, which in a way undermined social solidarity, political stability and state legitimacy and including heightened identity based power struggle. Although the EPRDF era registered positive record in terms of multilingual language policy as it was able to let the NNPs to use their language for education and in some cases for administration; however, EPRDF was also unable to promote national level multilingual policies for fostering cohesion. EPRDF's nation-building model didn't qualify for inclusive-polity model which may rather falls into the category of multinational-state model as which was emphasizing on distinctiveness/otherness, among others, failing to pay attention to nested identities.

Ethiopia needs an inclusive-polity building adhering to constitutional democracy, adopting multicultural policies at national level for ensuring inclusive citizenship, granting autonomy for asserting diversity, fostering nested identities (blending self-identity and shared identity), and forming an effective and smooth communication both vertically and horizontally among member states of the federation. In terms of language policy also switching from

one *lingua franca thesis* to *multiple lingua franca* as in the case of multicultural federations such as Switzerland, Belgium, Canada, India, and South Africa.

6. References

- Andreas Eshete. (2003). *Ethnicfederalism: New Frontiers in Ethiopian Politics*. Addis Ababa: United Printers plc.
- Assefa Fiseha. (2010). *Federalism and the accommodation of diversity in Ethiopia: A comparative study* (3rd ed.). Nijmegen: Wolf legal publishers.
- --. (2016). Intra-unit minorities in the context of ethno-national federation in Ethiopia. *Utrecht Law Review*, 13(1), 170–189.
- --. (2023). Federalism, devolution, and territorially-based cleavages in Africa: Does institutional design matter? In C. M. Fombad, F. Assefa, & N. Steytler (Eds.), *Contemporary Governance in the Horn Africa*. Routledge.
- Bahru Zewde. (2002). *A history of modern Ethiopia: 1855-1991* (2nd ed.). James Currey.
- Bender, M. L. (1985). Ethiopian Language Policy 1974-1981. *Anthropological linguistics*, 27(3), 273-279.
- --. (1983). The origin of Amharic. *Journal of the Institute of Language Studies*, 1(1), 41-50.
- Bengio, O. (2007). The Kurds and the state: Evolving national identity in Iraq, Turkey, and Iran. *Middle East Journal*, 61(4), 587-588.
- Berthele, R. (2021). The selective celebration of linguistic diversity: Evidence from the Swiss language policy discourse. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 42(2), 125-136.

- Bloor, T., & Tamrat, W. (1996). Issues in Ethiopian language policy and education. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 17(5) 321-337.
- Brubaker, R. (1996). *Nationalism reframed: Nationhood and the national question in the new Europe*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Cohen, G. P. E. (2000). *Identity and opportunity: The introduction of local languages for the purpose of primary education in the SNNPR, Ethiopia*. London University: PhD Thesis.
- Connor, W. (1972). Nation building or nation destroying? *World Politics*, 24(3), 319-355.
- (1976). Government language policy. In M. L. Bender, J.D. Bowen, R. L. Cooper, & C.A. Ferguson (Eds.), *Language in Ethiopia*. Oxford University Press.
- Cooper, R. L. (1989). *Language planning and social change*. Cambridge.
- Crummey, D. (2000). *Land and society in the Christian Kingdom of Ethiopia: From the thirteenth to the twentieth century*. University of Illinois Press.
- Ethiopian Census 2007. (2008). *Ethiopian population census communication*.
- Ethiopia. (1987). *The Constitution of the People's Democratic Republic of Ethiopia* (Proclamation No. 1). *Negarit Gazetta*, 47(1). Addis Ababa.
- Ethiopia. (1994). *The Constitution of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia*. Addis Ababa: Berhanena Selam.
- Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia. (1994). *Education and training policy*. Addis Ababa: Berhanena Selam.
- Fishman, J. A. (1972). *Language and Nationalism: Two Integrative Essays*. Newbury House.
- Getachew Anteneh, & Derib Ado. (2006). Language Policy in Ethiopia: History and Current Trends. *Ethiop. J. Educ. & Sc.*, 2(1), 37-62.
- Getahun Dilebo. (1974). *Emperor Menelik's Ethiopia, 1865-1916: National unification or Amhara communal domination*. Howard University: PhD thesis.
- Henze, P. B. (2000). *Layers of time: A history of Ethiopia*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Houser, G. M. (1987). Assessing Africa's Liberation Struggle. *Africa Today*, 34(4), 17-32.
- Hyslop, B. F. (1960). The American Press and the French Revolution of 1789. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society*, 104(1), 54-85.
- Khapoya, V. B. (2015). African Nationalism and the Struggle for Freedom. In *The African Experience* (pp. 139-167). Routledge.
- Kymlicka, W. (1995). *Multicultural citizenship: A liberal theory of minority rights*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- (2001). *Politics in the vernacular: nationalism multiculturalism and citizenship*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- --. (2007). *The rise and fall of multiculturalism? New debates on inclusion and accommodation in diverse societies*.
- Levine, D. N. (1974). *Greater Ethiopia: The Evolution of a Multiethnic Society*. University of Chicago Press.

- Lijphart, A. (2004). Constitutional design for divided societies. *Journal of Democracy*, 15(2), 96-109.
- , Consociationalism and federalism: Conceptual and empirical links. *Canadian Journal of Politics*, 12(3), 499-515.
- , (1975). *The politics of accommodation: Pluralism and democracy in the Netherlands*. Berkeley, Calif: University of California Press.
- Marcus, H. G. (1994). *A History of Ethiopia*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Markakis, J. (1974). *Ethiopia: Anatomy of traditional polity*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- , (2011). *Ethiopia: The last two frontiers*. Oxford: James Currey.
- , Schlee, G., & Young, J. (2021). *The nation state: A wrong model for the Horn of Africa*. Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften.
- May, R. J., & Regan, A. J. (Eds.). (1997). *Political decentralization in a new state: The experience of provincial government in Papua New Guinea*. Bathurst, Australia: Crawford House Publishing.
- McGarry, J., & O'leary, B. (2003). *Federation, conflict-regulation and national and ethnic power sharing: A paper prepared for annual meeting of the American political science association*.
- Mekuria Bulcha. (1997). The politics of linguistic homogenization in Ethiopia and the conflict over the status of Affan Oromoo. *African Affairs*, 9(6), 325-352.
- Merera Gudina. (2003). *Ethiopia: Competing ethnic nationalisms and the quest for Democracy, 1960-2000*. Addis Ababa: Shaker Publishing.
- Ministry of Education (MOE). (2002). *The education and training policy and its implementation*. Addis Ababa: Berhanena Selam.
- Moore, M. (Ed.). (1998). *National self-determination and secession*. Oxford University Press.
- Nodia, G. (2017). The end of the post-national illusion. *Journal of democracy*, 28(2).
- Norman, W. (2006). *Negotiating nationalism: Nation-building, federalism, and secession in the multinational state*. Oxford University Press.
- Ottaway, M. (2002). Think again: Nation building. *Foreign Policy*, (132), 16-24.
- Pankhurst, R. (1976). Historical Background of Education in Ethiopia. In Bender, M.L. et al. (eds.), *Language in Ethiopia*, 305-323.
- , (1990). *A Social History of Ethiopia: The Northern and Central Highlands from Early Medieval Times to the Rise of Emperor Tewodros II*. Addis Ababa University Press.
- Patel, J. (2018). Role of teachers in nation building. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 2(5), 2086-2089.
- Pye, L. W. (1962). *Politics, personality, and nation building: Burma's search for identity*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Rosenfeld, C. P. (1979). Eight Ethiopian women of the —Zemene Mesafintñ (c. 1769-1855). *Northeast African Studies*, 1(2), 63-85.
- Rubenson, S. (1966). *King of Kings: Tewodros of Ethiopia*. Addis Ababa: Haile Selassie I University.
- , (1976). *The survival of Ethiopian independence*. Heinemann Educational Books.

- (ed.) (1987). *Correspondences and treaties 1800-1850*. Addis Ababa University Press.
- Samuel, C. B. (1999). Building A Nation. *Transformation: An International Journal of Holistic Mission Studies*, 16(4), 141–144.
- Sergew Hable-Selassie. (1972). *Ancient and medieval Ethiopian history*: Institute of Ethiopian Studies: Addis Ababa University.
- Seyoum Tefera. (1996). Attempts at Educational Reform in Ethiopia: A Top-Down or a Bottom-Up Reform? *Ethiopian Journal of Education*, 16(1), 1-37.
- Smith, A.D. (1995). *Nations and nationalism in a global era*. Cambridge: Polity.
- Smith, A.D. (1998). *Nationalism and modernism: A critical survey of recent theories of nations and nationalism*. London: Routledge.
- Spolsky, B. (2004). *Language Policy*. Cambridge University Press.
- Stepan, A., Linz, J., & Yadav, Y. (2011). *Crafting state-nations: India and other multinational democracies*. Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Stepan, A. (1999). Federalism and democracy: Beyond the US model. *Journal democracy*, 10(4), 19-33.
- Tanner, A. (2006). Switzerland: a European Model of Liberal Nationalism?. *Liberty and the search for identity*, 109.
- Teshome Wagaw. (1997). Education and language policy in a divided Ethiopia: Reversing the quest of the centuries and pressing the uncharted future. In K. Fukui, E. Kurimoto, & M. Shigeta (Eds.), *Ethiopia in broader perspective*, 391-400. Kyoto: Nakanishi.
- Tilly, C. (Ed.). (1975). *The formation of national states in Western Europe*. Princeton University Press.
- Tollefson, J. W., & Pérez-Milans, M. (2018). Research and practice in language policy and planning. *The Oxford handbook of language policy and planning*, 1-32.
- Zelealem Leyew. (2012). The Ethiopian language policy: A historical and typological overview. *Ethiopian Journal of Languages and Literature*, 12(2), 1-59.